

Conversion of Used Goods to Prevent Children Consumptive Behaviour in Kesetnana Village, South Central Timor, Indonesia

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Abstract:

This community service activity was carried out in Kesetnana Village with the number of community service participants, namely 8 children. The stages in this activity are: Preparatory stage, at this stage the community service team conducts site visits and initial observations at community service locations to see first-hand the conditions and problems faced by children, namely community service activities that have been carried out are considered monotonous and the material presented has been forgotten by children so that children need new material and learning styles. Furthermore, the community service team coordinated with the local RT head to carry out community service activities. The implementation of the initial activity program was carried out by inviting the children to collect used bottles, small cardboard boxes, and other needed waste. After the tools and materials have been collected, while the community service participants provide the

material, the children are given the opportunity to practice the material provided. Furthermore, the community service team asked questions to the children regarding the activities carried out and checked success according to the targets set. The method used is the socialization method and direct practice of using used goods. This community service activity has succeeded in achieving its main goal, namely in addition to preventing consumptive behaviour in children, children also gain knowledge about how to reduce plastic waste around the environment. After the dedication was completed, the level of concern and creativity of children towards cleanliness and environmental health began to increase. This can be seen from the enthusiasm of the children in finding plastic waste and managing the existing waste into various kinds of handicrafts besides piggy banks, namely plastic flowers and so on.

Keywords: *community service, waste recycling, society, children.*

Introduction

Garbage is the result or consequence of human activity which is so complex. Human activity

inevitably produces waste, starting from waking up to going back to sleep. The volume of waste is proportional to the level of use of

goods/materials on a daily basis. More and more, more and more plastic waste, because humans use it a lot for various purposes. Garbage causes water, soil and air pollution, kills many animals and plants and also accelerates global warming. The use of second-hand goods reduces waste, which can prevent pollution while protecting the environment. Using used goods can reduce waste, especially plastic waste which is very difficult to decompose. Using used goods can increase the value of these items. For example, used cardboard is considered useless. However, after recycling, its utility value increases.

Handling waste globally is called the 3R method or Reduce, Reuse, Recycle. It is a step by step process that starts when no waste is generated. Not the effort that was made after the trash appeared. Reducing waste is the first step that needs to be done. This is real action before it becomes trash. This is a preventative or preventative measure to avoid wastage. An example of reduction is carrying a durable or reusable shopping bag instead of a plastic bag that is usually single use. There are many other examples of preventive measures that can be used. This includes the decision to use unpackaged non-organic, ecological laundry soap for kitchen furniture made with organic ingredients such as lime or pineapple instead of industrial products that are widely available in the market. With the size of this reduction must pay attention to products that do not pay attention to quality. For example, shopping bags that are not made of plastic are made of hard materials or fabrics, but of poor quality (sewn). Other examples are the recycling of used paper into new paper, the recycling of plastic into handicraft products, and the recycling of various materials such as metal and glass into new items. Non-plastic materials with poor manufacturing quality will certainly make the product unsustainable. This will be much more dangerous because the materials used are less environmentally friendly and will last longer than plastic when the soil decomposes. The challenge is to involve millions and billions of the world's population in implementing waste reduction actions. This is because most people want to

adopt an instant lifestyle, which is usually equated with non-bio-packaging disposable products. Using used goods can reduce waste, especially plastic waste which is very difficult to decompose. Waste that is not treated properly can of course contribute to environmental pollution. Pollution can pose a threat to ecosystem development. The threat to ecosystem development is not a group responsibility, but a collective responsibility. Therefore, we need the next generation who care about environmental sustainability.

If used properly, plastic waste can be used to create interesting and selling works. Before giving, of course, the plastic must be melted. Plastic can be processed by adding other materials, so that when it is processed into plastic handicraft products it becomes more stable and easy to shape. Creative products must have strong properties, good design, economy and light weight. Because of these properties, plastic is very suitable as a material for making handicrafts. Sewing, combining and combining with other materials.

Based on a preliminary survey conducted by the community service team, many children do not know that plastic waste such as used bottles can be used as useful objects such as piggy banks and wall or room decorations. Consumptive behaviour and frugal lifestyle must be learned early on, because these basic skills develop from the age of seven and can then be internalized in the character, behaviour and use of children's finances correctly and intelligently. They grow This is expected to create an economically competent workforce for a more advanced Indonesia.

According to Amaliya (2017), human consumption is characterized by a life of luxury and excess. The application of consumptive behaviour requires a lot of money, the use of which is considered the most expensive can bring satisfaction and joy to those who follow it. Consumerism is done to show social status, wealth, prestige, and to please followers. The formation of consumer behaviour has become part of the lifestyle process. Meanwhile, Lestarina et al (2017) divided aspects of

consumer behaviour into three parts, namely impulsive purchases, waste and lust. According to Triyaningsih (2011) who says that consumer behaviour is formed by: Buying items that are not so important therefore becomes excessive. The young age group is the main protagonist of a consumptive lifestyle. This behaviour can take root in a teenager's lifestyle. In its development they are always mature with a consumptive lifestyle.

Figure 1a. A Savings Box Made of Used Materials and Clay

Figure 1b. A Savings Box Made of Used Materials and Clay

The existence of plastic that accompanies us in everyday life. Most of the plastic we use just becomes trash and accumulates. According to Nasuoni, Siti et al. (2018) "It takes tens or even hundreds of years for used plastic waste to decompose completely naturally." The problem, however, is that the negative impact of plastic waste is as great as its function. The plastic

recycling (recycling) process reduces the amount of plastic waste in the area, resulting in a healthier environment and communities benefit from increased income when plastic can be recycled into beautiful, marketable crafts. Also people should try not to depend on plastic to reduce the amount of plastic waste. Or if plastic addiction is hard to break, you can learn how to take care of used plastic and it is still suitable for use or switch to other materials that easily decompose in the environment, so that plastic production can be reduced.

The use of used goods can reduce consumer behaviour. Instead of continuing to buy things we don't need, we are more creative and maximize what we have.

Materials and Methods

For the utilization of goods and shells used as handicrafts as part of a housewife's charitable activities. Using the implementation method through socialization and direct practice of utilizing used goods into useful goods. Recycling used goods into durable goods to prevent children's consumption behaviour is divided into two stages: 1. situation analysis report, 2. preparation of materials to be distributed to children, 3. Preparation of methods and tools and materials used 4. Learning the process of making savings boxes of the resulting material. The analysis carried out relates to the subject of waste management in such a way that it becomes a product that can be sold or an object that has economic value other than the value of waste that was previously deemed useless through interrogation techniques. For the utilization of goods and shells used as handicrafts as part of a housewife's charitable activities. Using the implementation method through socialization and direct practice of utilizing used goods into useful goods. The return of used goods into useful goods to prevent children's consumption behaviour is divided into two stages: 1. situation analysis report, 2. preparation of materials for transfer to children, 3. preparation of methods and tools and materials, 4. Teaching the process of making a Savings Box from these materials material made. The analysis carried out is related

to the subject of waste management by turning it into products or objects that can be sold with economic value other than the value of waste that was previously deemed useless by interrogation techniques.

Methodology

This community service implementation activity was carried out in Kesetnana Village with the number of community service participants, namely 8 children. The stages in this activity are: (1) The preparatory stage, at this stage the community service team conducts site visits and initial observations at the community service location to see firsthand the conditions and problems faced by the children, namely the community service activities that have been carried out are considered monotonous and the material is delivered has been forgotten by children so that children need new material and learning styles. Furthermore, the community service team coordinated with the local RT head to carry out community service activities. Furthermore, the preparation of material that will be delivered by the community service Team and methods that match the community service title. After that, the community service team gathered children from RT 012 RW 005 as community service participants. Socialization or introduction of material and explanations about the method of how to use plastic waste to make piggy banks began. The implementation of the initial activity program was carried out by inviting the children to collect used bottles, small cardboard boxes, and other needed waste. After the tools and materials have been collected, while the community service participants provide the material, the children are given the opportunity to practice the material provided. Furthermore, the community service team asked questions to the children related to the activities carried out, and checked success according to the targets set.

Results and Discussion

This community service activity was carried out with children from RT 012 RW 005 as

community service subjects. This activity is part of an effort to carry out community service to reduce plastic waste around the environment while preventing consumptive behaviour in children by accustoming children to utilizing used goods around them so that they become useful items.

Before children are given the opportunity to practice how to process plastic waste or the tools they carry, children are first given an explanation about the dangers of plastic waste for themselves and the surrounding environment with the aim that children really understand the dangers of not protecting nature and littering. This activity also aims to make children more creative and able to process used items around them into useful items without having to buy them.

In general, community service activities run smoothly according to the plans that have been made. This community service has succeeded in achieving its main goal, namely that apart from preventing consumptive behaviour in children, children also gain knowledge about how to reduce plastic waste around the environment. After the service is completed, the level of concern and creativity of children towards cleanliness and environmental health begins to increase. This can be seen from the enthusiasm of the children in finding plastic waste and managing the existing waste into various kinds of handicrafts besides piggy banks, namely plastic flowers and so on.

However, there are still some obstacles related to the prevention of consumptive behaviour in children, namely

- 1) Low understanding of the impacts and dangers of plastic waste from the local community is evident in the large amount of waste that is scattered and disposed of carelessly even though community service activities have been carried out.
- 2) The lack of parental attention to the warnings given by children who have attended community service.
- 3) There are no community activities related to community creativity programs in the local RT

so that prevention of consumptive behaviour by using used goods is difficult to follow up on.

Conclusions

By reducing the amount of plastic waste through 3R, we can overcome the problem of plastic waste in the environment which greatly affects the beauty of the landscape, disturbs our health and affects our activities. One of them is a recycling process such as making beautiful handicrafts from plastic which have a selling point so that they can reduce consumptive behavior in children. The use of used goods can reduce consumptive behavior and encourage a thrifty lifestyle. Where we prefer to use used materials rather than buying new things. This allows us to save money and avoid unnecessary plastic usage.

References

- Lestarina, E., Hasnah, K., Nia, F., Ranny, & Desi, H. (2017). Consumptive Behaviour Among Teenagers. *Indonesian Action Research Journal*, 2(2), 1-6.
- Lina, L., & Rosyid, H.F. (1997). Consumptive behavior based on locus of control in young women. *Psychology: Journal of Psychological Thought and Research*, 2(4), 5-14.
- Nasution, S.R., Rahmalina, D., Sulaksono, B., & Doaly, C. O. (2018). IbM: Pemanfaatan limbah plastik sebagai kerajinan tangan Di Kelurahan Srengseng Sawah Jagakarsa Jakarta Selatan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Teknik Industri*, 6(2), 117-123.
- Triyaningsih, S.L. (2011). Dampak Online Marketing melalui Facebook terhadap Perilaku Konsumtif Masyarakat. *Ekonomi dan Kewirausahaan*, 11(2), 172-177.